

Specific features of solving the housing problem in our country in the context of economic reforms

Termez Institute of Economy and Service

Phd. Norqobilov N
student Abdullayev J

Abstract

The article examines the problems of providing housing to the population in the regions of our country and analyzes the existing housing funds, their condition and living conditions. market mechanisms are effective in solving the problem by applying conclusions, recommendations and suggestions for solving this problem are given.

Аннотация

Мақолада мамлакатимиз ҳудудларида аҳолини уй-жой билан таъминлаш муаммоларини ўрганишб, мавжуд уй-жой фондлари, уларнинг ҳолати ҳамда яшаш шарт-шароитлари таҳлил қилинган.Шунингдек, ҳудудларда аҳолини уй-жой билан таъминлаш таҳлили асосида мавжуд муаммони ечишда, бозор механизмларини самарали қўллаш йўли билан бу муаммони ечиш бўйича хулоса, тавсия ва таклифлар берилган.

Аннотация

В статье изучены проблемы обеспечения жильем населения в регионах нашей страны, проанализированы существующие жилищные фонды, их состояние и условия проживания. Также при решении существующей проблемы на основе анализа обеспеченности жильем населения в регионах даны выводы, рекомендации и предложения по решению этой проблемы путем эффективного применения рыночных механизмов.

Key words: Population, enterprise, budget, pension, salary, construction

Ключевые слова: Население, предприятие, бюджет, пенсия, заработная плата, строительство.

Калит сўзлар: Аҳоли, корхона, бюджет, пенсия, иш ҳақи, қурилиш.

Introduction

The issue of providing housing to the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan is important in the current period of reforming society and forming socially oriented market relations. It is known that providing housing to the population is one of the necessary means of ensuring the well-being of human life, and it performs a very important task of providing the basic link of society - the family with favorable conditions for building and strengthening it.

The main part

The study of the problems of providing housing to the population requires the analysis of housing construction based on a systematic approach, taking into account the existing housing stock, their condition, and the growth of the requirements for living conditions.

It should be noted that the needs of the population are formed not only by the objective growth of the general requirements of living comforts and the growth of sanitary and hygienic conditions, but also by the significant expansion of the scope of consumption requirements in the context of the social stratification of the population.

Currently, sufficient attention is being paid to the problems of housing and housing use in our republic. Here we present many decrees of the President of the Republic and decisions of the

Cabinet of Ministers (the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 17, 2021 No. 576 "Measures to ensure the preparation of social sector objects of economic sectors and multi-apartment housing stock for stable operation in the autumn-winter period of 2021/2022 on the activities of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of April 24, 2017 PQ-2922 - con " On the capital and current repair of the common areas of the multi-apartment housing fund in 2017-2021 " The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 22, 2017 "On amending the regulation on the privatization of the state housing fund in the Republic of Uzbekistan"...) .

The main purpose of these documents is to provide state support and social protection to the needy sections of the population in solving the housing problem, and additional incentives for the future development of housing construction carried out at the expense of the enterprise, association organizations and the population.

In general, they reflect the influence of state bodies in solving the main problems of ensuring strong social protection of the population based on the requirements of the market economy.

The demographic features of the population in Uzbekistan have a growing tendency, the total population is 0.9 million annually on average. making up a person, and the share of adolescents under the age of 18 is more than 40% of the total population. Three quarters of the population live in rural areas.

The mentioned statistical data testify to the relevance of issues related to the development of housing construction, and this in turn leads to the provision of the housing fund in different regions, regions, cities and rural areas due to the growth of different rates .

The construction industry of Uzbekistan is defined as a priority sector of the economy. The modern construction industry is one of the most prominent national sectors of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, showing steady annual growth rates. The number of enterprises and organizations operating in the field of construction can be seen in the section of the following areas of this field; - buildings and constructions construction direction made up 56.8% of the share, and the growth rate increased by 106.7% compared to the corresponding period of 2021; - the direction of construction of civil objects made up 10.8% of the share, and the growth rate increased by 117.4% compared to the corresponding period of 2021; - specialized construction works made 32.4% share and 104.1% growth rate. In 2022, the total volume of construction works amounted to 130,790.9 billion soums ¹. At present, the need for housing in the regions of the country is met mainly through individual construction.

According to the results of the analysis of the demographic and housing fund situation in our country and its growth rate, the amount of housing construction in Uzbekistan is insufficient. It is necessary to implement the necessary measures in order to reach the level of developed countries in this field.

Currently, the comfort level of the existing housing fund does not meet the requirements of the time. This is reflected in the fact that the costs of their use cannot be reached to the optimal level due to the inconveniences in the beauty of this fund, the ease of its constructive solution, the volume-design structure and, most importantly, the design structure.

¹ Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan data. 2022 [www. lex.uz](http://www.lex.uz)

Solving the problem of providing housing is related to the need to significantly increase the volume of construction and develop all elements of the infrastructure of cities and settlements of Uzbekistan, in which progressive approaches are used.

Also, the unique demographic situation in our republic has a certain effect on the growth of social indicators of providing housing to the population under the conditions of ongoing economic reforms. The following factors need to be taken into account when solving this problem:

- the limitation of land areas allocated for construction and the need for priority development of mass multi-storey housing construction;
- the need to take into account the process of social stratification of the society and the expansion of the requirements for living conditions along with it;
- due to population growth in rural areas. This leads to the enlargement of the existing rural settlements and the change of their position;
- the level of comfort of the existing housing stock is not high;
- the objective increase of requirements for modern and comfortable housing as a result of scientific and technical development in the country.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in solving this problem, there are positive results and achievements achieved through the effective use of market mechanisms. However, to solve this problem on a large scale, it requires marketing research aimed at a deeper analysis of the state of housing construction and the formed housing market.

List of used literature:

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